

Extreme Heat Exposure in the First 1,000 Days: Implications for Childhood Stunting in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Objectives: Stunting is a critical public health issue in Bangladesh, a country highly vulnerable to climate change and increased extreme heat exposure. Limited research has examined the relationship between extreme heat during the first 1,000 days of life and stunting. This study provides the first evidence from Bangladesh on the likelihood of stunting among children aged 24–59 months following exposure to extreme heat during this crucial developmental period.

Study Design: The study utilized district-level panel data from the 2012 and 2019 Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys, including 24,035 children aged 24–59 months, paired with daily temperature records.

Methods: A multilevel logistic regression model with district-level random effects assessed the relationship between extreme heat exposure and stunting.

Results: A 1% increase in extreme heat days during the first 1,000 days of life was associated with higher odds of stunting (adjusted odds ratio [AOR] 1.56, 95% confidence interval [CI] 1.25–1.95, $p < 0.0001$) at 24–59 months of age. Post-birth exposure to extreme heat showed a stronger association with stunting (AOR 1.67, 95% CI 1.37–2.03, $p = 0.063$) than in utero exposure (AOR 1.28, 95% CI 1.14–1.44, $p < 0.0001$).

Conclusion: Escalating extreme heat threatens decades of progress in reducing stunting in Bangladesh. Mitigation efforts targeting the first 1,000 days of life are critical, alongside further research to disentangle the specific effects of extreme heat on child growth within the broader context of climate change.

Key words: Stunting; Extreme heat; Climate change; First 1,000 days; Child growth; Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Stunting, a result of chronic malnutrition, leads to impaired physical and cognitive growth with lasting consequences, including reduced educational attainment and lifetime earnings. The Lancet Series on maternal and child undernutrition (2021) highlighted the critical first 1,000 days of life, from utero to 23 months of age, as crucial for growth and development¹. Nutritional deficits during this period are difficult to reverse and can lower lifetime earnings by over 7%^{1,2}. In Bangladesh, the prevalence of stunting among children under five years declined from 42% in 2012–13 to 28% in 2019, due to improvements in maternal education and nutrition, infant and young child feeding practices, food security, water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH), and women's empowerment^{3,4}. However, the stunting rate remains higher than the global average of 22%, with recent years showing signs of slowed progress^{4,5}.

The role of climate change as a driver of nutritional outcomes is gaining increasing attention⁶. It is predicted that between 2030 and 2050, there will be 2.5 million additional deaths attributed to climate change from malnutrition and heat-related illnesses along with diarrhea and malaria⁷. Bangladesh ranked among the most climate-vulnerable nations, has seen significant increases in

the frequency and intensity of heat waves^{8,9}. The observed number of days exceeding 35°C from 1971 to 2020 increased by 14.04 days per decade in the country¹⁰. Whether increasing extreme heat exposure has contributed to the prevalence of stunting is unexplored in the country.

Notwithstanding the importance, global evidence directly linking extreme heat exposure to growth faltering remains limited and fragmented^{11–13}. Among several pathways, extreme heat exposure during pregnancy can lead to oxidative stress and inflammation, damaging placental tissues and impairing its function¹⁴. This results in placental insufficiency, reducing oxygen and nutrient delivery to the fetus, increasing risks of intrauterine growth restriction, low birth weight, and preterm birth — conditions that are significant risk factors for stunting^{14–16}. A meta-analysis of 70 studies across 24 countries, including seven low- and middle-income countries, found that a 1°C rise in ambient temperature increased the odds of preterm birth by 1.05 (95% CI 1.03–1.07) and the odds of low birth weight by 1.09 (IQR 1.04–1.47), with mothers from lower socioeconomic backgrounds being disproportionately affected¹⁵. A study of the coastal population of Bangladesh reported a negative association between days of heat exposure above 35°C and lower mid-upper arm circumference at birth¹⁷.

Heat exposure has a more pronounced effect on infants than on adults. Infants have an underdeveloped thermoregulation system leading to a lower rate of sweat production and lower skin surface area to dissipate heat¹⁸. At the same time, infants have a higher metabolic rate per unit mass than adults and a higher metabolic cost of activities due to proportionately larger organs than among adults, thereby increasing energy expenditure while attempting to keep the body cool¹⁸. In addition, heat stress can lead to maternal dehydration, which can reduce breast milk production and induce dehydration¹⁹. The conditions are further exacerbated by diminished appetite brought on by the heat²⁰. An increase in heat has been linked to a higher burden of infectious diseases such as diarrhea, that diminish an infant's ability to absorb nutrients^{1,9}. Tusting et al.¹³, studying the relationship between heat exposure and growth faltering among children under 5 years using cross-sectional data from 52 Sub-Saharan African countries reported a higher association between exposures days above 35°C and the odds of wasting (OR 1.27, 95% CI 1.16–1.38; $p < 0.0001$), underweight (OR 1.09, 95% CI 1.02–1.16; $p = 0.0073$), and concurrent stunting with wasting (OR 1.23, 1.07–1.41; $p = 0.0037$). Counterintuitively, heat was negatively associated with the prevalence of stunting (OR 0.90, 95% CI 0.85–0.96; $p = 0.0009$). Blom et al.¹¹ projected a 7.4% increase in stunting prevalence with a 2°C rise in average temperature, based on the cumulative effects of heat during the first 90 days of life in a cross-sectional study in West Africa.

Though the health literature has not defined specific safe heat exposure thresholds for human health, most studies rely on absolute temperature limits—typically between 35°C and 37°C—beyond which harm to the body may occur^{11,13,21}. However, this approach has limitations, as people living in hotter climates adapt to regular heat exposure through physiological changes. Heat acclimatization results in increased sweat production, earlier onset of sweating, and lower core body temperature during physical activity in hot conditions²², improving cardiovascular function and heat tolerance²³. Despite these adaptations, they are often insufficient to cope with unusually intense heat waves and even heat exposure beyond historical norms can be harmful, leading to increased heat-related illness and mortality²¹. Consequently, using uniform thresholds may result in over- or underestimations in analyses.

This paper examines the association between cumulative extreme heat exposure—defined as temperatures above the 80th percentile compared to historical trends—during the critical first 1,000 days of a child’s life and stunting in children aged 24–59 months in Bangladesh between 2012 and 2019. We further analyze the comparative magnitude across the association while in utero and 0–23 months. Using a district-level panel dataset from the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS), this study makes several significant contributions to the emerging climate and child health literature. It is the first to explore the association between cumulative extreme heat exposure during the first 1000 days and linear growth faltering in Bangladesh and the region, focusing on an often-overlooked age group. This is crucial, as previous research has shown that environmental factors, including extreme heat, are more strongly linked to stunting in children aged 24–59 months than in those under 24 months, with stunting taking longer to manifest and becoming more common after two years of age²⁴. Furthermore, the study employs an adaptive temperature model to better contextualize heat exposure, making its findings particularly relevant given Bangladesh’s vulnerability to climate change. Projections suggest a rise in extreme heat days—from 129.5 days between 1995 and 2014 to 172.1 days between 2040 and 2059—highlighting the urgency of understanding how climate change may exacerbate chronic undernutrition in climate-vulnerable low-and-middle income countries like Bangladesh.

2. Methods

2.1 Data and variables

The height-for-age (HAZ) z-scores for children aged between 24 to 59 months were extracted from the MICS, conducted in 2012/13 and 2019^{25,26}. The MICS, designed as a repeated cross-sectional survey based on a two-stage random cluster sampling strategy and representative of all 64 districts in the country, collected a host of individual and household level information on child health and nutrition, maternal health, reproductive health, water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH), child protection, and relative wealth status, among other factors. In 2012/13, the MICS sampled 51,895 households, and in 2019, 61,242 households across the country. Households with children aged 24 to 59 months were selected for analysis, comprising 11,549 children in 2012/13 and 12,486 in 2019, resulting in a pooled sample of 24,035 children. A two-round district-level panel dataset was constructed for analysis. Further details on the MICS sampling methodology and measured outcomes are available in the cited reports^{25,26}.

The MICS collected data on height, weight, sex, and age (by month) for all children in the surveyed households, with anthropometric z-scores provided in the survey data for children under five, calculated using the World Health Organization Growth Standards²⁷. The primary outcome of interest is a binary indicator reflecting whether a child aged 24 to 59 months is stunted in each survey round. The indicator takes on the value of 1 for children whose height-for-age (HAZ) z-score is lower than two standard deviations (SD) below the reference population median, and 0 otherwise²⁷.

District-specific temperature data was gathered from the Enhancing National Climate Services for Bangladesh Meteorological Department (ENACTS-BMD) dataset that amalgamates high-resolution ($0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ gridded) daily maximum dry-bulb temperature data for Bangladesh, derived from various sources including weather stations and reanalysis-based temperature data²⁸. Extreme heat

was defined as the number of days when the maximum dry-bulb temperature exceeded the 80th percentile, based on a 10-year, month-on-month reference period for the warm months (March–November) preceding the 2012 and 2019 survey rounds ²¹. The monthly totals were aggregated to estimate each child’s total exposure to extreme heat in utero, 0-23 months of age, and pooled to reflect the first 1,000 days, determined by their date of birth.

2.2 Analytical approach

The association between the prevalence of stunting among children aged 24 to 59 months and the number of days of exposure to extreme heat (log-linear) during the first 1,000 days of life was analyzed using a population-weighted bivariable and multivariable multilevel logistic model, with random effects at the district level, based on the pooled sample. A similar model was estimated to examine the difference in the magnitude of association between extreme heat exposure during gestation and during the 0 to 23-month period. The choice of random variability for district-level effects was made to incorporate unobserved factors that vary across districts, allowing the model to capture variability without providing specific estimates for each district. Additionally, this approach ensured that the random effect did not induce multicollinearity or confounding in the relationships among other covariates.

The multivariable models adjusted for a variety of sociodemographic and environmental factors known to influence stunting, as highlighted in the existing literature, to isolate the contribution of extreme heat exposure to stunting, minimizing bias and providing a clearer understanding of its relationship.^{1,3,15} Child-specific factors included the child’s age (categorized as 36 to 47 months and 48 to 59 months versus 24 to 35 months), biological sex (male versus female), whether the child experienced diarrhea in the two weeks preceding the survey, and whether the child had ever been breastfed¹. Perinatal factors were also considered, such as the season of birth to account for ambient conditions (monsoon: July-September, post-monsoon: October-November, winter: December-February, and pre-monsoon: March-May) and maternal age at childbirth (grouped in five-year increments from 20 to 49 years, compared to 15 to 19 years). Maternal education level was accounted for, with categories ranging from below primary education (reference) to completed primary, and secondary education or higher.

Household characteristics were incorporated into the model, including the biological sex of the household head (female versus male), relative wealth quintiles (with comparisons of each quintile to the poorest), and household location (rural versus urban). Additionally, the model included a binary indicator for represented access to improved WASH facilities, coded as improved if the household reported having access to sanitary latrines and improved handwashing facilities, “unimproved” otherwise.

The standard errors for all models were clustered at the level of the sampling unit. The results from the bivariable and multivariable models are presented as odds ratios (OR) and adjusted odds ratios

¹ Two of the control variables, whether a child has been breastfed and components of the WASH indicator had missing values in the data. Given their relative importance as determinants of stunting, the missing values were imputed to maximize the sample size. Further details of the imputation methods and robustness checks of the updated data are detailed in Appendix A.

(AOR) respectively with a 95% confidence interval. A prespecified p-value of less than 0.1 was considered statistically significant for the analysis. All analyses were done using STATA 18.1.

3. Results

The results are based on a pooled sample of children aged 24 to 59 months from surveys conducted in 2012 and 2019 across 64 districts in Bangladesh. Summary statistics are presented in Appendix B. Among the 24,035 children in the sample, 8,099 (33.3%) were aged 24-35 months, 8,074 (33.6%) were aged 36-47 months, and 7,952 (33.1%) were aged 48-59 months. Approximately 12,497 children (52.0%) were male. Only 942 children (3.9%) reported having diarrhea in the two weeks preceding the survey. The rate of breastfeeding was nearly universal, with 23,337 children (97.1%) having been breastfed at some point. Additionally, 5,731 children (23.8%) were born during the pre-monsoon season, 7,912 (32.2%) during the monsoon, 4,250 (17.7%) during the post-monsoon, and 6,142 (25.6%) during the winter.

At the time of childbirth, 755 mothers (3.1%) were aged 15-19 years, 6,506 (27.1%) were aged 20-24 years, 7,705 (32.0%) were aged 25-29 years, 5,086 (21.2%) were aged 30-34 years, and 3,983 (16.6%) were aged 35-49 years. Approximately 6,223 mothers (25.9%) had attained primary education, while 8,623 (35.9%) had secondary or higher education, and 9,189 (38.2%) had not completed primary education. In terms of living conditions, 16,023 households (66.7%) had access to safe WASH facilities, and 4,126 households (17.2%) were located in urban areas.

The pooled number of days with extreme heat and the mean of the daily maximum DBT, are presented in Table 1. The mean exposure to days with extreme heat during the first 1,000 days across the pooled sample was 169.7 (SD 27.5) days for the sample. The daily mean of the maximum temperature for the corresponding extreme hot days was 29.7°C (IQR 23.9–35.5°C). While the absolute number of extreme hot days was higher in 2019 than in 2012—175.3 and 164.6 days respectively—the daily mean of the maximum temperature was higher in the later year: 29.9°C (IQR 24.2–35.6°C) in 2019, compared to 29.6°C (IQR 24.4–34.8°C) in 2012. The full temperature range across the corresponding years is presented in Appendix C.

>>Table 1 goes here<<

The weighted prevalence of stunting among children aged between 24 to 59 months in Bangladesh is presented in Figure 1. The first column shows the mean across the pooled sample, followed by the prevalence across the survey rounds in 2012 and 2019. The pooled national weighted prevalence of stunting for the cohort of interest was 38.5% (95% CI 37.8-39.1), with a notable decrease between 2012 and 2019 from 47.4% (95% CI 46.5-48.3) to 30.1% (95% CI 29.3-30.9). The prevalence of stunting reduced as children aged (24-35 months: 41.9% [95% CI 40.9-43.0]; 36-47 months: 40.0% [95% CI 38.9-41.1]; and 48-59 months: 33.4% [95% CI 32.3-34.4]). Stunting among female children was marginally higher than among male children, 39.7% (95% CI 38.8-40.6) versus 37.3% (95% CI

36.5-38.2) respectively. At the sub-national level, the proportion of stunted children was higher in rural areas, 39.8% (95% CI 39.1-40.5), than in urban ones, 31.9% (95% CI 30.5-33.4).

>>Figure 1 goes here<<

Results from the bivariable and multivariable analyses assessing the association between exposure to extreme heat during the first 1000 days and the prevalence of stunting among children aged 24-59 months are shown in Table 3. The bivariable analysis indicated that a 1% increase in the number of days with extreme heat was associated with lower odds of stunting (OR 0.87, 95% CI 0.74–1.02, $p=0.097$). In the adjusted model, increased exposure to extreme heat was associated with higher odds of stunting (AOR 1.56, 95% CI 1.25–1.95, $p<0.0001$).

Next, we assessed the heterogeneity in the association between extreme heat and stunting across the period in utero and in children aged 0-23 months. A 1% increase in days with extreme heat while in utero was associated with higher odds of stunting in both the bivariable (OR 1.30, 95% CI 1.18–1.44, $p<0.0001$) and adjusted models (AOR 1.28, 95% CI 1.14–1.44, $p<0.0001$). For children aged 0-23 months, increased exposure to extreme heat lowered the odds of stunting in the bivariable analysis (OR 0.65, 95% CI 0.58–0.73, $p<0.0001$), but the odds increased significantly in the adjusted model (AOR 1.67, 95% CI 0.99–1.37, $p=0.063$).

>>Table 2 goes here<<

4. Discussion

This study establishes a robust association between cumulative exposure to extreme heat during the first 1,000 days of life and stunting among children aged 24–59 months in Bangladesh. Specifically, a 1% increase in the total number of extreme heat days is associated with a 56% increase in the odds of stunting. The observed differences in timing of exposure are particularly noteworthy, with exposure during the 0–23-month period associated with a stronger effect (67%) compared to in-utero exposure (28%). These findings emphasize the importance of early-life stages in determining long-term growth outcomes and underscore a critical window for intervention, as catch-up growth beyond 59 months is increasingly difficult¹.

Prior evidence on this topic has been limited and predominantly focused on Africa^{11,13,15}. Nonetheless, our findings largely align with this body of evidence linking extreme heat exposure to adverse child health outcomes, while addressing the critical research gap in South Asia. Blom et al.¹¹ demonstrated significant reductions in height-for-age z-scores in West Africa, with stunting prevalence increasing by 7.4% in response to a 2°C rise in average temperature. Similarly, Chersich et al.¹⁵ identified high temperatures during pregnancy as critical risk factors for preterm birth and low birth weight, which are known precursors of stunting. Our findings, however, vary from Tusting et al.¹³, who observed stronger associations between heat exposure and wasting rather than

stunting in African children. These discrepancies may reflect regional variations in adaptation, socio-economic conditions, or measurement methodologies. Stunting, as a chronic condition, may take longer to manifest, whereas wasting often represents an acute response to environmental stressors²⁴.

Mechanistic pathways provide important context for interpreting these findings. Heat-induced oxidative stress and inflammation may impair placental function, reducing oxygen and nutrient transfer to the fetus¹⁴. These effects may persist into early childhood, as infants are particularly vulnerable to heat stress due to underdeveloped thermoregulatory systems and higher metabolic demands¹⁸. Maternal dehydration during heat waves may further exacerbate nutritional deficits by reducing breast milk production¹⁹. Prolonged exposure to heat has also been linked to increased diarrheal disease burden, which impairs nutrient absorption and exacerbates undernutrition^{12,16,21}. Together, these pathways highlight the complex and multifactorial impacts of heat exposure on child growth.

These findings underscore the urgent need for climate-resilient public health strategies tailored to mitigate the effects of extreme heat. Existing maternal and child health programs must be strengthened to incorporate heat resilience through capacity building, targeted behavior change communication, and enhanced care delivery. The non-government sector, both for profit and non-government organizations (NGOs), can strongly complement these identified areas. More specifically, NGOs can leverage the community network to deliver heat-resilient interventions, such as promotion of heat-safe practices for mother and child care, nutrition and health education and importance of hydration and adequacy of food intake both by pregnant mothers and the young child during a heat event and distribution of low costing cooling technologies. For profit entities can contribute through innovative solutions such as affordable cooling devices and climate resilient agricultural practices to promote food security. Both public and NGO-led social protection initiatives, such as cash transfers or food assistance, could help buffer the economic and nutritional impacts of extreme heat on vulnerable households. These programs should be integrated into broader climate and health communication strategies by the governments and the non-government sector to sustain recent gains in child health and nutrition. As extreme heat events are expected to increase in both frequency and intensity, targeted interventions, facilitated by multisectoral collaboration, are essential for reducing stunting and improving child health outcomes^{8,9}.

While this study makes significant contributions to understanding the direct impacts of extreme heat on stunting, the study has some limitations. The reliance on district-level temperature data may not fully capture microclimatic variations at the household level, potentially leading to exposure misclassification. Additionally, while several sociodemographic factors were controlled for, unmeasured confounders, such as detailed infant and young child feeding practices, birth weight, skilled birth attendance, or gestational age, may have influenced the observed associations. Finally, the repeated cross-sectional design limits causal inference, emphasizing the need for longitudinal studies to better understand the chronic effects of heat exposure on growth trajectories. Future research should also explore other climate stressors, such as humidity or flooding, which may compound the impacts of extreme heat on child health in Bangladesh^{12,21}.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates a significant direct relationship between cumulative extreme heat exposure during the first 1,000 days of life and stunting in children aged 24-59 months in Bangladesh. The findings underscore the urgency of integrating climate change mitigative strategies into public health and nutrition interventions by both the government and non-government sectors aimed at addressing chronic malnutrition in climate-vulnerable regions. As global temperatures continue to rise, understanding the direct impact of extreme heat on child health is essential for safeguarding future generations from the adverse effects of climate change.

Data Sharing

The paper is based on secondary publicly available data from: <https://mics.unicef.org/surveys> and <https://dataportal.bmd.gov.bd/>

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI to support copy-editing. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of Interest: None

Ethical considerations

This study is based on secondary analysis of publicly available, anonymized data from the 2012 and 2019 Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS). As such, no direct ethical approval was required. This secondary analysis complies with ethical guidelines for the use of de-identified data and does not involve any identifiable information.

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Tables and figures

Table 1 Relative extreme heat exposure, and temperature range, for children aged 24-59 months during their first 1000 days.

	Pooled		2019		2012	
	Days with extreme heat	Temperature range (Maximum DBT)	Days with extreme heat	Temperature range (Maximum DBT)	Days with extreme heat	Temperature range (Maximum DBT)
	Mean (SD)	Mean (IQR)	Mean (SD)	Mean (IQR)	Mean (SD)	Mean (IQR)
First 1000 days (gestation to 23 months)	169.7 (27.5)	29.7 (23.9-35.5)	164.6 (17.1)	29.9 (24.2-35.6)	175.3 (34.6)	29.6 (24.4-34.8)
In utero	62.4 (17.8)	29.5 (23.7-35.4)	59.4 (14.2)	29.9 (24.2-35.6)	65.7 (20.6)	29.3 (24.3-34.3)
0-23 months of age	107.3 (23.9)	29.8 (24.0-35.6)	105.2 (10.8)	29.8 (24.4-35.2)	109.6 (32.6)	29.7 (24.3-35.1)

Note: Extreme heat is defined as temperatures exceeding the 80th percentile, calculated and aggregated separately for each month based on data from the 10 years preceding each survey round. The temperature range reflects maximum DBT during days with excess heat.
 IQR = Inter-quartile range; DBT = dry-bulb temperature

Table 2 Association between days with extreme heat exposure (log-linear) during (1) the first 1000 days, and (2) in utero, and 0-23 months, and the odds of stunting among children aged 24-59 months.

Covariates/Factor	Bivariable model		Multivariable model (1)*		Multivariable model (2)*	
	Unadjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
First 1000 days	0.87 (0.74-1.02)	0.097	1.56 (1.25-1.95)	<0.0001		
In utero	1.30 (1.18-1.44)	<0.0001			1.28 (1.14-1.44)	<0.0001
0-23 months	0.65 (0.58-0.73)	<0.0001			1.67 (0.99-1.37)	0.063

Note: * The models were adjusted for age and biological gender of the child, whether the child has been breastfed, seasonality of childbirth, maternal age and education at childbirth, WASH status, biological gender of the household head, relative wealth quintiles, and whether in an urban or rural location. The full model is presented in Appendix D. n = 24,035 (pooled), 11549 (2012) and 12486 (2019)

Figure 1 Weighted prevalence of stunting (CI 95%) among 24-59-month-old children. N = 24,035 (pooled), 11,549 (2012) and 12,486 (2019).

	Pooled	2012	2019	
Overall	38.5 37.8-39.1	47.4 46.5-48.3	30.1 29.3-30.9	
National	24-35 months	41.9 40.9-43.0	50.7 49.1-52.3	34.3 32.9-35.7
	36-47 months	40.0 38.9-41.1	49.5 47.9-51.1	31.1 29.7-32.6
	48-59 months	33.4 32.3-34.4	42.2 40.7-43.8	24.7 23.4-26.0
	Female	39.7 38.8-40.6	48.5 47.2-49.8	31.4 30.2-32.6
	Male	37.3 36.5-38.2	46.4 45.2-47.7	29.0 27.9-30.1
	Subnational	Rural	39.8 39.1-40.5	49.0 48.0-50.0
Urban		31.9 30.5-33.4	38.9 36.6-41.1	26.5 24.7-28.3